

The influence of sol–gel processing parameters on the photochromic spectral and dynamic behaviour of a naphthopyran dye in an ormosil coating

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A photochromic naphthopyran derivative was embedded in a Ph-modified ormosil coating. Important changes in the photochromic properties of the films were induced by modifications in the preparation parameters of the sol–gel processing, such as the hydrolysis and condensation of the sols, the photochromic-dye loading in the film and the curing of the samples after deposition. In this way, it is possible to control the thickness of the resulting coatings, their absorption spectra after irradiation and the kinetics of thermal bleaching. The coatings were prepared having a thickness in the 0.8–2.1 mm range, allowing the incorporation of large amounts of dye in the matrix (up to a dye/Si molar ratio of 0.02) and showing a coloration change upon irradiation with UV-light in the ΔOD 0.04–0.22 range.

Introduction

The sol–gel process, being a low temperature method, can be used for the preparation of hybrid organic–inorganic ormosil matrices.^{1–3} The method allows the introduction of a large number of organic molecules into the matrix, conferring their specific properties to the resulting inorganic or ormosil glassy network.^{4,5}

Naphthopyran derivatives constitute an important group of molecules, having a pyranic heterocycle, which exhibit very interesting photochromic properties. The photoinduced cleavage of the C(sp³)–O bond of the pyran ring leads to the formation of colored merocyanine structures,⁶ as shown in Fig. 1. The system reverts through a thermal pathway to its original closed form.

The most important properties of these molecules are their absorption spectra upon irradiation with UV light, particularly the position of the absorption maximum and the intensity of color obtained, and the kinetics of the bleaching (*i.e.* recovery of the original whiteness). The photochromic properties of the naphthopyrans have been measured in solvents^{7,8} and polymeric matrices.^{9–11} In a previous work, we have demonstrated the feasibility of introducing photochromic naphthopyran derivatives into sol–gel ormosil matrices.¹² In solid matrices

the photochromic properties of the embedded molecules are strongly influenced by the polarity of the environment where the molecules are located.¹³ Moreover, the size and shape of the pores containing the dye molecules have also an important effect on the spectral and kinetic properties of the photochromic system, as they may provoke steric inhibitions during molecule opening–closing process.¹² Recently, we reported on the introduction of different functional groups into ormosil networks and its effect on the photochromic properties of the embedded naphthopyran molecules.¹⁴

The objective of the present work is to modify and optimize the spectral and dynamic behaviour of the photochromic naphthopyran molecules embedded in ormosil thin films, adjusting specific sol–gel preparation parameters such as: the hydrolysis and condensation of the alkoxide precursors in the sol (time and temperature), the amount of dye in the matrix or the curing process of the samples after deposition. These changes will affect the chemical composition of the pore surface (organic embedded functional groups/OH groups ratio) and the structure of the pores containing the dye molecules. The ability to control the photochromic properties of a coating by properly adjusting the parameters of the sol–gel processing will be of great interest from the point of view of future applications.

Fig. 1 Bleached and colored forms of photochromic naphthopyrans.

Experimental

Materials

Tetracetoxyasilane (TAS) was from ABCR. Phenyl triethoxy-silane (PhTES) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Aldrich Chemicals. Ethanol was from Merck. For all preparations double-distilled water was used. The photochromic dye used for the preparation of samples, 3-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3H-naphtho[2,1-b]pyran, was generously donated by PPG Industries, Inc. The chemical structure of the dye is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Chemical structure of the naphthopyran dye used for preparation of samples.

Preparation of coatings

Samples were prepared from mixtures of TAS, PhTES and water in a TAS : PhTES : H₂O molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 7. The phenyl-modified matrix was chosen due to its high capacity to accommodate the organic dye and the ability to prepare relatively thick films. The reaction was self-catalyzed by the slow release of acetic acid from the TAS during hydrolysis. The sols were allowed to hydrolyze under stirring, at constant temperatures (T_{hyd}) between 5 and 45 °C with hydrolysis times (t_{hyd}) between 0 and 24 h. The photochromic dye was added as a THF solution, after the hydrolysis of the sol, to obtain the required photochromic-dye : Si molar ratios. THF was used as solvent due to the possibility to obtain highly concentrated solutions and good miscibility with the coating sol.

The deposition of the films was carried out after the addition of the dye using the spin-coating technique. Films were prepared by dropping 0.1 mL of the sol onto a spinning sample holder (2000 rpm). The films were cured at 100 °C for periods of time ranging from 0 and 166 h.

Characterization

The photochromic samples were irradiated with a 365 nm, 100 W, B-100AP UV lamp from UVP. The absorption spectra of the resulting films as well as the kinetics of the bleaching were measured in a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The absorption spectra were measured between 300 and 800 nm, and are given as DAbs ($A_{\text{a.i.}}$ $\mathbf{2}$ $A_{\text{b.i.}}$), where $A_{\text{a.i.}}$ and $A_{\text{b.i.}}$ are the absorption after and before irradiation, respectively. The bleaching kinetics were monitored *vs.* time at the wavelength of the maximum absorption of each sample (visible range) at 25 °C. The kinetic constants were calculated from the bleaching curves using a bi-exponential decay equation. t_{K} is defined as the time required by the sample to reach $\text{DAbs}_{\text{max}}/2$ during the thermal bleaching. The thickness of the films was measured with a Taylor-Hobson Form Talysurf-50 profile analyzer.

Results and discussion

The photochromic properties of the naphthopyran dye dispersed in a phenyl-modified ormosil matrix were modified by controlling different parameters of the sol-gel processing, namely the time and temperature of the hydrolysis and condensation of the initial sol, the relative amount of the dye incorporated in the matrix and the curing time of the samples

after deposition. The composition of the ormosil host matrix, however, remained the same for all samples, limiting the effect of the changes to the structure of the matrix.

Hydrolysis and condensation: time (t_{hyd}) and temperature (T_{hyd}) of the hydrolysis

The hydrolysis and condensation processes start with the addition of water to the alkoxide precursors. During these processes the formation and progressive growing of primary silica/ormosil particles takes place. This particle formation is strongly influenced by the rates of hydrolysis and condensation, which in turn depend on the temperature of the reaction. Once the sol acquires a certain degree of hydrolysis it can be deposited on glass substrates. The condensation will then be strongly accelerated due to massive evaporation of the solvents, forming a transparent thin film.

In order to study the effect of the hydrolysis and condensation on the photochromic properties of the coatings, samples were prepared allowing the sol to hydrolyze for different periods of time, keeping constant all other preparation parameters including temperature, which was kept at 25 °C. The results are summarized in Table 1. The minimum hydrolysis time required to obtain transparent samples is about 4 h. Shorter hydrolysis times results in the precipitation of the dye as soon as it is added to the sol. At the early stages of the condensation process, the high amount of uncondensed OH groups is responsible for the highly polar environment in the sol, resulting in a very low solubility of the dye. The polarity of the sol is progressively reduced as the condensation of the OH groups proceeds allowing the incorporation of the dye into the sol and the deposition of transparent films.

The absorption spectra (position and intensity of the absorption band) of the photochromic films after irradiation with UV light were not affected by the time of hydrolysis, implying that the pore environment remained unaffected. The thickness of the films, however, was slightly increased in samples prepared with longer hydrolysis times due to the increased viscosity of the sols.

An interesting behaviour was observed in the bleaching kinetics of samples prepared with different t_{hyd} . The samples exhibited higher fading rates in the dark (faster thermal bleaching) as the hydrolysis time was increased. The measured bleaching curves, represented as $\mathbf{2}\ln(\text{DAbs})$ *vs.* time, are shown in Fig. 3. The kinetic data of the representative samples measured are summarized in Table 1. The slower bleaching kinetics observed in samples with t_{hyd} $\mathbf{5}$ 7 h is related to a lower relative amount of Ph groups in the pore surface. The presence of Ph groups in the matrix-dye interface boosts the bleaching kinetics of the naphthopyran dyes in sol-gel prepared ormosil matrices.¹⁴ The hydrolysis and condensation rates of alkoxides are much higher than those of organically modified alkoxides: In mixtures of silicon alkoxides and ormosils, the sol can be considered as growing silica clusters having the ormosil as a co-solvent,¹⁵ increasing their size as the hydrolysis proceeds. Immediately after the deposition of the film, the rapid release of solvents leads to the condensation of the phenyl-modified alkoxides at the surface of the silica primary particles. The larger the silica primary particles at the

Table 1 Spectroscopic properties of the samples prepared with different hydrolysis times at 25 μ C. All samples have a dye : Si ratio of 0.005 : 1 and curing time of 24 h

t_{hyd}/h	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$	DAbs ($A_{\text{a.i.}}$ \cdot $A_{\text{b.i.}}$)	Thickness, e/mm	Clear film	Kinetic constants		
					$k_1/10^{23} \text{ s}^{-21}$	$k_2/10^{23} \text{ s}^{-21}$	t_{rc}/s
2.00	—	—	—	7	—	—	—
4.00	488	0.098	—	37	—	—	—
7.00	487	0.103	1.30	3	12.6	0.64	522.0
15.00	488	0.108	1.35	3	17.1	0.68	492.0
24.00	490	0.109	1.38	3	22.2	0.86	316.4

Fig. 3 Thermal bleaching kinetics of photochromic samples with different hydrolysis times at 25 μ C.

Fig. 4 Absorption spectra of the samples prepared with different temperatures of hydrolysis.

time of deposition, the larger the relative amount of Ph groups on the surface of the resulting pores.

The temperature of the hydrolysis (T_{hyd}) has also an important effect on the photochromic properties of the resulting thin films. Samples were allowed to hydrolyze for 24 h at different temperatures between 5 and 45 μ C, keeping constant all other parameters. The absorption spectra of samples prepared with different T_{hyd} , after irradiation with UV light, are shown in Fig. 4. The positions of the absorption maxima of the samples remained constant at λ 490 nm despite the T_{hyd} used. However, an increase in both the intensity of the band and the thickness of the films was observed as the T_{hyd} was increased, as shown in Table 2. Both the hydrolysis and condensation processes in the sol are accelerated by increased temperature. For a given t_{hyd} , higher T_{hyd} leads to the formation of larger silica primary particles in the sol, resulting in an increase of the viscosity and therefore a thicker spin-coated film. The intensity of the absorption maximum as well as the thickness of the films, depicted as a function of T_{hyd} , are shown in Fig. 5a. The absorption intensity, however, after being normalized with the thickness according to Beer Lambert's law, decreased considerably with the increase of T_{hyd} , as shown in Fig. 5b. At higher T_{hyd} , the polarity of the pore environment is reduced due to the higher relative amount of Ph groups (vs. OH groups) that interact with naphthopyran molecules inside the pore cage.¹⁴ The latter results in higher stabilization of the closed form of the photochromic molecule

reducing therefore the color intensity of the sample after irradiation.

The T_{hyd} , although affecting strongly the spectral behaviour of the photochromic samples, has no influence on the bleaching kinetics, all samples having k_1 and k_2 kinetic constants of about 0.019 s^{-21} and $7.9 \cdot 10^{24} \text{ s}^{-21}$ respectively. We should expect similar behaviour to that observed for different t_{hyd} at 25 μ C, where the bleaching was considerably accelerated upon increasing the hydrolysis time from 0 till 24 h. This effect, however, can only be observed at the first stages of the hydrolysis when a rapid growth of the silica particles occurs. After 24 h of hydrolysis the size of the primary silica particles in the sol stabilizes, and even though condensation of the sol continues to take place, it has very limited effect on the relative amount of phenyl groups on the pore surface of the resulting film, and hence on the interaction between the dye and the pore surface.

Table 2 Spectroscopic properties of the samples prepared with different temperatures of hydrolysis. All samples were hydrolyzed for 24 h, using a dye : Si ratio of 0.005 : 1 and cured at 100 μ C for 24 h

$T_{\text{hyd}}/\mu\text{C}$	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$	DAbs ($A_{\text{a.i.}}$ \cdot $A_{\text{b.i.}}$)	Thickness, e/mm	(DAbs/ e)/ nm^{-21}
5	490	0.093	0.90	0.103
15	490	0.106	1.23	0.088
25	490	0.109	1.38	0.079
35	492	0.128	1.87	0.068
45	492	0.137	2.10	0.065

Fig. 5 (a) Influence of the temperature of the hydrolysis on the DABs ($A_{\text{a.i.}}$ \bullet $A_{\text{b.i.}}$) and the thickness of the resulting samples. (b) The intensity of the absorption maximum of the irradiated samples normalized with the thickness.

Concentration of photochromic dye in the matrix

The amount of photochromic dye that is incorporated in the ormosil matrix is a key issue to determine the intensity of the absorption of the resulting coating. At the same time, the addition of very large amounts of naphthopyran to the composition will lead to the precipitation of the dye in the pores hindering the photochemical ring opening process. Therefore, it is important to optimize the concentration of dye as a function of the overall performance of the photochromic coatings. In the samples described here, a linear increase of the DABs ($A_{\text{a.i.}}$ \bullet $A_{\text{b.i.}}$) of the irradiated samples was observed as the dye/Si ratio was increased reaching a saturation value around dye/Si \bullet 0.02 as shown in Table 3. The absorption spectra of irradiated samples prepared with different amounts of dye are shown in Fig. 6. The position of the absorption band, being around 490 nm, is not affected by the amount of dye in the matrix. The thickness of the coating decreased as higher dye/Si ratios were used. This issue, shown in Fig. 7a, is due to the dilution of the sol by the addition of the dye solution (in THF). The DABs at the maximum absorption of the samples normalized with their thickness is given in Fig. 7b. The kinetics of the thermal bleaching was not affected by the amount of dye embedded in the matrix.

Table 3 Spectroscopic properties of the samples prepared with different dye/Si ratios

Dye/Si molar ratio	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$	DABs ($A_{\text{a.i.}}$ \bullet $A_{\text{b.i.}}$)	Thickness, e/mm	(DABs/e)/mm \bullet ²¹
0.0025	490	0.046	1.40	0.033
0.0050	490	0.109	1.38	0.079
0.0075	490	0.113	1.23	0.092
0.0100	489	0.154	1.20	0.128
0.0125	488	0.170	1.15	0.148
0.0150	488	0.174	1.10	0.158
0.0175	490	0.202	0.93	0.217
0.0200	490	0.212	0.91	0.233
0.0225	490	0.180	0.91	0.198
0.0250	492	0.209	0.89	0.235
0.0275	492	0.209	0.88	0.237
0.0300	490	0.213	0.85	0.251

Fig. 6 Absorption spectra of the samples prepared with different amounts of dye.

Curing time

The samples after deposition must undergo a heat treatment in order to consolidate the structure of the embedding matrix and allow the formation of a mechanically stable coating. At room temperature this process is very slow and could take months to achieve a stable coating. On the other hand, at high temperatures the organic dye may decompose, losing its photochromic properties. The curing temperature was therefore set to 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, achieving stable layers in a reasonable period of time and avoiding the decomposition of the dye in the matrix. The time of curing was found to have an important effect on the properties of the photochromic coatings. Samples prepared with 24 h of hydrolysis at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a dye : Si ratio of 0.005 : 1 were cured after deposition for different periods of time, ranging from 0 to 166 h. The photochromic properties of these samples are summarized in Table 4. The absorption spectra of the samples, after irradiation with UV light, are given in Fig. 8. The absorption maxima of the samples (λ_{max}) showed a progressive shift to lower wavelengths with

Fig. 7 Effect of the amount of dye on the spectroscopic properties of the samples (a) DAbs ($A_{a,i}$ \bullet $A_{b,i}$) and thickness. (b) DAbs ($A_{a,i}$ \bullet $A_{b,i}$) normalized with the thickness of the samples.

increasing time of curing, reaching a constant value after approximately 24 h as shown in Fig. 9. At the same time, a decrease in both the DAbs ($A_{a,i}$ \bullet $A_{b,i}$) at the band maxima and the thickness of films was observed in the first 24 h of curing, as shown in Table 4, reaching then a constant value. The DAbs as a function of the curing time is given in Fig. 9, after normalization with the thickness. The relatively slow thermal bleaching kinetics observed for as-deposited dry samples was progressively accelerated (decrease of t_R) with the curing of the samples, as shown in Fig. 10. The kinetic data

Table 4 Spectroscopic properties of the samples with different curing time at 100 μC

Curing time/h	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$	DAbs ($A_{a,i}$ \bullet $A_{b,i}$)	Thickness, e/mm	(DAbs/e)/nm ²
0	498	0.124	1.57	0.078
5	492	0.125	1.44	0.087
15	490	0.111	1.39	0.080
24	488	0.109	1.38	0.079
48	488	0.103	1.38	0.075
72	488	0.111	1.38	0.081
96	488	0.099	1.38	0.072
120	488	0.092	1.38	0.067
144	488	0.107	1.38	0.078
166	488	0.090	1.38	0.065

Fig. 8 Absorption spectra of samples prepared with different curing times.

Fig. 9 Effect of the curing time on the spectroscopic properties of the resulting coatings.

of the representative samples measured are summarized in Table 5. All these observations can be explained by the progressive condensation of the glass matrix during the curing process, releasing water and solvents and leading to a closer pore structure, increasing hence the chemical and steric interactions between the photochromic molecules and the matrix pore surface.¹² Differently to the effect of the hydrolysis time on the bleaching kinetics, which is due to the concentration of phenyl groups on the pore surface, the curing time affects the steric interactions between the dye and the pore surface due to the contraction of the pore walls during the curing process.

Conclusions

The photochromic properties of naphthopyran molecules embedded in Ph-modified ormosil matrices were modified by adjusting several preparation parameters of the sol-gel processing, namely the time and temperature of hydrolysis and condensation of the sols, the loading of the photochromic dye in the films and the curing time of the films after

Fig. 10 Thermal bleaching kinetics of the photochromic effect in samples prepared with different curing times (at 100 uC).

Table 5 Kinetic data of the thermal bleaching of photochromic samples with different curing time

Curing time/h	Kinetic constants		
	$k_1/10^{23} \text{ s}^{-21}$	$k_2/10^{23} \text{ s}^{-21}$	t_K/s
0	9.6	0.58	496.6
5	17.2	0.75	378.5
24	22.2	0.86	316.4
96	26.6	1.02	265.2

deposition. These parameters affect the size and shape of the pores, where the dye molecules are located, and the chemical composition of the pore surface (phenyl groups/OH groups ratio) and then, provide a way of controlling the photochromic properties of the naphthopyran in the ormosil matrix such as the absorption spectra of the coating after irradiation and its bleaching kinetics. In the same way, the thickness of the resulting films can be controlled between 0.8 and 2.1 mm. The resulting ormosil coatings show a very high dye loading in the matrix (dye/Si ratio of 0.02), allowing the preparation of strongly colored devices.

The ability to control the interaction between an active molecule and its embedding ormosil matrix opens a new way of tailoring the performance of the resulting sol-gel based devices.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by CICYT-MAT2001-1053 research project. The authors are grateful to PPG Industries Inc. for the generous donation of the photochromic molecule used in this work. Rosario Pardo is grateful to MEC for a doctoral studentship and Marcos Zayat is also grateful to CAM for a postdoctoral fellowship.

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